

Kinetics and mechanism of electron-transfer reactions : Oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide by iodine monochloride in acid aqueous medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide by iodine monochloride has been studied in acid aqueous medium. The reaction stoichiometry is represented by

The reaction exhibits first order kinetics with respect to the oxidant but a complex order with the substrate. The rate law is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{ICl}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_h[\text{ICl}][\text{DMSO}]}{K_h + [\text{H}^+] + K_h[\text{DMSO}]}$$

Thermodynamic parameters have also been evaluated.

Keywords : Iodine monochloride, kinetics, electron transfer reaction, oxidation, dimethyl sulfoxide, mechanism.

Introduction

Cihalik and co-workers¹ pointed out the possibility of using iodine monochloride as an oxidimetric reagent. The direct reaction with iodine monochloride can be achieved in acid medium, however, it is not suitable for indirect determinations in alkaline medium owing to the formation of hypoiodite which itself can be an oxidimetric reagent.

Iodine monochloride similar to iodine can be applied in titrimetric analysis. The iodine monochloride in contrast to an iodine solution is, however, more stable, less costly and more widely applicable².

Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) has been extensively employed as a solvent and a chemical reagent apart from biochemical wastage of disposal treatment in industrial waste water. However, oxidation to sulfone occurs with various reagents³. Kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide by a number of oxidants have been reported employing *N*-halosulfonamides⁴.

These were the reactions of halo sulfonamides that

prompted us to undertake the title reaction from the following view point. First, whether or not the reactions of iodine monochloride and *N*-halosulfonamides respectively with DMSO take place on the same pattern of reactivity. This, is an important question to probe further. Secondly whether or not the reaction indicates any adduct formation or simply occurs through bimolecular interactions. Thirdly whether or not hydrogen ion dependence, if any, comes from iodine monochloride or dimethyl sulfoxide in such reactions.

Experimental

Iodine monochloride solution was prepared by oxidizing iodide with iodate in hydrochloric acid medium. ($2\text{I}^- + 6\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 3\text{I}^+ + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Iodine monochloride solution (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared by dissolving 11.068 g potassium iodide in 50 cm^3 water. To this was added a solution of 7.134 g potassium iodate in 250 cm^3 water and the mixture was immediately followed by addition of 200 cm^3 concentrated hydrochloro-

ric acid free from iron(III) and chlorine. The solution was made up to 1000 cm³. The preparation of iodine monochloride was controlled visibly².

Such a solution is reported to be practically stable if the acid concentration is maintained to ~1.0 mol dm⁻³. The solution was standardized iodometrically. All other reagents (AnalaR) and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water except ICl solution which was prepared in triple distilled water. The second distillation of water was made with alkaline permanganate solution in an all glass apparatus. However, third distillation by adding EDTA in doubly distilled water made it free from metal ions particularly iron(III) ions.

The reactions were carried out at a constant temperature in a thermostat (±0.1 °C). All ingredients except ICl were taken in one flask and solution of iodine monochloride was taken in another one. A known volume of iodine monochloride of desired concentration was withdrawn and then immediately added into the reaction mixture. The remaining ICl was estimated iodometrically.

Since the reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ([ICl] << [DMSO]), pseudo-first order plots were made and rate constants (*k'*, s⁻¹) were calculated. The reactions in triplicate were reproducible to within ±5%. A few reactions under kinetic conditions with an excess of iodine monochloride over [DMSO] were allowed to occur in a thermostated water bath at 40 ± 01 °C for ca. 2 h. The excess iodine monochloride was estimated iodometrically. Stoichiometric results indicate that one mole of iodine monochloride reacts per mole of dimethyl sulfoxide.

The product sulfone was established spectrally. However, attempts made to isolate the product by diethyl ether was failed.

The IR spectral analysis of the oxidation product of DMSO exhibits two absorption bands in the region 1350–1400 and 1050 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching of SO₂ group. The absorption band at 520 cm⁻¹ is also observed due to the

bending vibrations of SO₂ group. Two absorption bands appeared below 3000 cm⁻¹ at 2950 and 2850 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric C–H stretching vibrations respectively. The kinetic results on the other hand also established sulfone to be the oxidation product of dimethyl sulfoxide.

Results and discussion

[ICl] was varied (1.0 – 5.0 × 10⁻³) mol dm⁻³ at 40 °C. *k'* (s⁻¹) decreases little with [ICl] due to decrease in [acid]. The concentration of dimethyl sulfoxide was varied from 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ at 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively. Pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from a plot of (*k'*, s⁻¹) versus [DMSO] initially increases with concentration of the substrate and then tends to attain a limiting value at higher concentrations.

The rate of the reaction increases with [LiClO₄].

The effect of hydrogen ion was studied by employing perchloric acid 0.5 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at constant ionic strength (*I*). The rate of the reaction decreases slightly with increasing hydrogen ion concentration.

† Thus the following reaction mechanism in view of hydrogen ion dependence and other experimental observations can be envisaged as follows :

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (5) or (6)

$$-\frac{d[\text{ICl}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_h[\text{DMSO}][\text{ICl}]}{K_h + [\text{H}^+] + KK_h[\text{DMSO}]} \quad (5)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{ICl}]/dt}{[\text{ICl}]} = k' = \frac{kK_h[\text{DMSO}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{DMSO}]} \quad (6)$$

where *k'* and [DMSO] are observed for first order rate constant and free equilibrium concentration of dimethyl sulfoxide, respectively.

Since the rate decreases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration and DMSO forms an adduct, the rate law (6) accounts for the experimental observations. Taking double reciprocal of eq. (6), eq. (7) is obtained.

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[H^+] + K_h}{kKK_h[DMSO]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

A plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[DMSO]$ was made from eq. (7) which yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1). ' k' ' (s^{-1}) was calculated from the intercept to be $(4.1 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-2}$, $(5.1 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-2}$ and $(6.7 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ at 40, 45 and 50 °C, respectively.

Fig. 1. Plot of k' versus $[DMSO]^{-1}$ in the reaction of iodine monochloride and dimethyl sulfoxide : (O) 40°; (Δ) 45° and (□) 50 °C.

Similarly a plot of $1/k'$ versus $[H^+]$ was made from eq. (7) at constant concentration of dimethyl sulfoxide which also yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept. The gradient (G) and intercept (I) calculated from this plot are given by eqs. (8) and (9) respectively.

$$G = 1/kKK_h[DMSO] \quad (8)$$

$$I = 1/kK[DMSO] + 1/k \quad (9)$$

The eq. (9) on rearrangement yields eq. (10)

$$(I - 1/k) = 1/kK[DMSO] \quad (10)$$

The ratio of $(I - 1/k)/G$ gives K_h to be 0.09 ± 0.01 , 0.1 ± 0.02 and $0.12 \pm 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively.

Similarly ' K ' was calculated from eq. (10) by rearranging it in the form of eq. (11),

$$K = 1/\left(I - \frac{1}{k}\right) \cdot k \cdot [DMSO] \quad (11)$$

Substituting the values of k and $[DMSO]$ in this eq. (11), K was calculated to be 25 ± 1 , 39 ± 2 and 60 ± 3 at 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively.

These values of k , K and K_h were further employed to recalculate rate constants (Table 1) and the values of k_{cal} and k_{exp} were in good agreement.

Table 1. Experimental (k_{exp}) and calculated (k_{cal}) rate constants in the reaction of iodine monochloride and dimethyl sulfoxide $[DMSO] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[ICl] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. (°C)	HClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)	LiClO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ (k_{exp}) (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ (k_{cal}) (s ⁻¹)
40	0.50	1.50	4.98	5.31
40	0.75	1.25	4.60	4.63
40	1.00	1.00	4.03	4.10
40	1.25	0.75	3.64	3.68
40	1.50	0.50	3.45	3.34
40	1.75	0.25	3.07	3.05
40	2.00	-	2.68	2.81
45	0.50	1.50	7.67	7.98
45	0.75	1.25	7.00	7.32
45	1.00	1.00	6.90	6.76
45	1.25	0.75	6.52	6.28
45	1.50	0.50	6.14	5.87
45	1.75	0.25	5.75	5.50
45	2.00	-	5.37	5.18
50	0.50	1.50	10.0	10.7
50	0.75	1.25	9.5	9.98
50	1.00	1.00	9.1	9.28
50	1.25	0.75	8.95	8.67
50	1.50	0.50	8.63	8.14
50	1.75	0.25	8.31	7.67
50	2.00	-	7.67	7.25

So far the mode of electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant is concerned and the following Scheme 1 can be suggested.

The energy and entropy of activation for the rate controlling step were calculated to be $40 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-121 \pm 6 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The sufficiently large negative entropy of activation supports compact transition state in the reaction.

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